

WHAT ARE THE EDUCATIONAL LEVELS OF GREEK ORTHODOX IN AUSTRALIA IN 2021?

James A Athanasou

Independent Researcher, Sydney, Australia

athanasou@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this report is to provide an educational profile of the 390,963 Greek Orthodox in Australia. It is derived from the national census in 2021. Greek Orthodox are behind the general population in educational achievement in postgraduate qualifications and bachelor degrees. Their educational achievement is dominated by secondary education of Years 10 and above (26.9%). Comparisons were also made with six other faith groups (Buddhism, Christianity minus Greek Orthodox, Hinduism, Islam, Judaism, Secular Beliefs/No Religion). Greek Orthodox have the highest proportion (13.6%) of any group with Year 9 schooling and below which may reflect the older members and the migration pattern of this cohort. Overall, Hinduism and Judaism have higher levels of educational achievement than Greek Orthodox.

Keywords

Greek Orthodox, Australia, education, census

I. INTRODUCTION

Information about the educational background of a group may benefit health, educational, social or welfare services in a community. In a religious context, the level of educational achievement is a guide to reading competence, to comprehension and knowing at what level to provide information to a community. At the same time a group's level of education is also a reflection of socio-cultural circumstances and historical influences.

The purpose of this report is to cast an eye over the educational profile of the 390,963 people in Australia who indicate that they are Greek Orthodox. The report also compares Greek Orthodox with other faith groups in Australia. It is a small step towards an understanding of the socio-educational influence of a religion.

By way of background, there has been a previous analysis of Greek Orthodox in 2016 (Athanasou, 2022). That analysis showed a median level of educational achievement of Greek Orthodox in Australia of secondary education Years 10 and above. The report concluded:

The proportion of those with postgraduate degrees (3%) is far lower than those from Hinduism (23%) or Judaism (12%). The proportion of Greek Orthodox with a degree is 14% and again this compares poorly with Hinduism (32%),

Judaism (32%), Buddhism (21%), no religion (18%) or Islam (17%). Amongst Buddhism, other Christian, Hinduism, Islam, Judaism or no religion groups, the Greek Orthodox have the highest proportion (17%) of those with the lowest level of education (i.e., Year 9 and below) (p. 3)

The present report extends this analysis. The information from which it is derived is the response to the optional question on one's religion ("What is the person's religion?") in the 2021 national census. The Census collected information on educational achievement and it was a small step to cross-tabulate these findings. What can be determined for Greek Orthodox are: (a) their levels of educational achievement in 2016 and 2021; and (b) how they compare with other faith groups in terms of education.

Figure 1. Educational achievement of Greek Orthodox in 2021.

I. BACKGROUND

Greek Orthodox educational achievement in 2016 and 2021

The distribution of the level of educational achievement of Greek Orthodox in Australia is shown in Figure 1. It is

dominated by achievement at a level of secondary education of Years 10 and above (26.9%).

It is now possible to compare the 2021 Census with the 2016 Census and this comparison is provided in Table 1. There is an increase in the proportion of graduates and post-graduates, as well as advanced diplomas to Certificate III/IV level amongst Greek Orthodox. In all 37% have some form of post-school education or training. There is around a 5% increase in post-school education from 2016 to 2021. Secondly, there is a reduction in those with Year 9 or below and in the Other group. The tendency for educational credentials or achievement to increase across time is also the case in the wider population.

TABLE I

Educational achievement of Greek Orthodox in 2016 - 2021

Level of Highest Educational Attainment	2016	2021
Postgraduate Degree	2.3%	3.0%
Graduate Diploma/Certificate	1.1%	1.5%
Bachelor Degree Level	11.3%	13.5%
Advanced Diploma/Diploma	6.8%	7.5%
Certificate III & IV	11.1%	11.5%
Secondary Education - Years 10 and above	26.5%	26.9%
Secondary Education - Years 9 and below	14.4%	12.9%
Other	26.4%	23.1%

How do Greek Orthodox compare with the general population in Australia?

If anything, Greek Orthodox are behind the general population in educational achievement at the highest levels. It is the case for postgraduate level and bachelor degrees. The differences are shown in Figure 2 which compares the rest of Australia (minus Greek Orthodox) with Greek Orthodox.

How do Greek Orthodox compare with other faith groups in terms of education?

Comparisons were made between Greek Orthodox and other religious faiths of a migrant or non-English speaking background (e.g., Buddhism, Hinduism, Islam, Judaism), as well as with other Christians minus Greek Orthodox and a secular category or no religion.

The results for seven groups are summarised in Table 2. Hindus rank highest for graduate qualifications combined (49.3% for postgraduate, graduate certificates/diplomas or degrees). They are ahead of Judaism with 43.3% and well ahead of Greek Orthodox with 18.9%. The proportion of Greek Orthodox is fairly comparable with other Christians at 19.8% but lower than those with Secular beliefs or no religion at 23.1%.

At the other extreme, Greek Orthodox have the highest proportion (13.6%) of any group with Year 9 schooling and below which may reflect the older members of this cohort. At

the same time, they seem to have a very high proportion of persons who completed secondary schooling but did not complete post-school qualifications.

Figure 2. Educational achievement comparison of Australia (minus Greek Orthodox) with of Greek Orthodox in 2021.

II. CONCLUSIONS

There has not been any change in the median educational level of Greek Orthodox Australian from 2016 to 2021. The median level of educational achievement is still secondary education of Years 10 and above. That is, most Greek Orthodox complete the highest level of secondary schooling and nothing more. It is a broad guide to the level at which information and resources should be provided to the community.

One reason for the high proportion of Greek Orthodox with the highest level of education at Year 9 and below schooling may be attributed to the post-war migration of Greek Orthodox, which was centred on that period 1950-1970 and likely it comprised mainly those with a schooling of Year 9 and below.

In the history of migration to Australia, different religions and types of migrants dominated particular periods. The period of arrival in Australia is particularly important for Greek Orthodox. Southern Europeans (Greeks, Italians) dominated immigration from the post-war years until around 1970 and by all accounts they were mainly labourers. The more recent trend is for admission on the basis of pre-existing education or skill levels to fill differing needs in the economy. As a result the proportion of those

TABLE II

Educational achievement of six faith groups in 2021

	Buddhism	Christianity ¹	Hinduism	Islam	Judaism	Secular ²	Greek Orthodox
Postgraduate	8.6%	4.0%	22.2%	8.6%	11.7%	5.7%	3.2%
Grad Dip/Cert	1.7%	2.0%	2.1%	1.1%	3.6%	2.2%	1.5%
Bachelor Degree	20.7%	13.8%	25.0%	13.7%	28.0%	15.2%	14.2%
Diploma	9.5%	8.7%	7.8%	5.8%	8.4%	7.4%	7.9%
Certificate III/IV	6.9%	14.9%	3.6%	5.8%	5.1%	14.8%	12.1%
Year 10 and above	25.1%	26.9%	11.6%	22.1%	18.1%	25.1%	28.4%
Certificate I/II	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%
Year 9 and below	7.4%	7.7%	1.6%	6.0%	2.5%	4.6%	13.6%
Other	19.9%	21.8%	26.2%	36.8%	22.6%	24.9%	24.4%

¹Christianity less Greek Orthodox; ²Secular Beliefs and Other Spiritual Beliefs and No Religious Affiliation

Figure 3. Graduate qualifications vs Schooling Year 9 and below of persons who arrived in Australia 1905-2020.

migrants with secondary education of Years 9 and below has fallen dramatically over the period from 1951 to 2020. At the same time graduate qualification (post-graduate degree, graduate certificate or diploma or bachelor's degree) for those arriving in Australia increased markedly from 1961-70 to 2011-2020. That trend may benefit some ethnic, national or religious groups and the overall pattern is shown in Figure 3.

In terms of the influence of a religion, there is evidence that faith interacts with educational achievement. Overall, Hinduism and Judaism have higher levels of educational achievement than Greek Orthodox but also the other faith

groups (Buddhism, Other Christian, Islam, Secular/No religion). It is especially the case for Hinduism, where they rank highest for graduate qualifications combined (49.3% for postgraduate, graduate). The relationship, however, is more complex than a simple linear comparison and may involve a cocktail of sociocultural, ethnic, migration and policy factors.

What can one say about the future levels of educational achievement of Greek Orthodox? It is likely that they will be affected by the increase in credentials in Australia. More people now complete high school and go on to tertiary study than in the past. Additionally the educational level of Greek Orthodox will be influenced by other factors such as a reduction in the older and less-educated age groups in the Greek Orthodox population; the increasing extent to which English is the language used; the socio-economic or socio-cultural background; the opportunities available to people; and overall inter-generational mobility of Greek Orthodox. Nonetheless, the median level of educational achievement is still around Years 10-12 and this might act as a guide to the reading or comprehension levels for information and texts for Greek Orthodox in Australia.

Funding Preparation of this report received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial or not-for-profit sectors.

Declaration of competing interest There is no competing interest and the author has no financial disclosure.

Ethical statement: the research was conducted in accordance with the principles embodied in the Declaration of Helsinki and in accordance with local statutory requirements.

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